

Bacteria in land-based larval rearing systems: sources of bacteria and their quantitative and qualitative influence on the microbiota of rearing water and larvae

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ABSTRACT

In aquaculture, mortality and poor performance during early life stages remain major bottlenecks. It is well-documented that detrimental larvae-microbe interactions significantly cause these problems. To develop microbial management strategies, it is crucial to understand where microbes in the rearing tank come from, what determines their community composition, and how microbes from live feed and water affect the gut microbiota of larvae. This study aimed to combine previously published and new data to address these questions for the larval rearing of Atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua* L.). Three rearing system designs were analyzed: a flow-through system (FTS), a FTS with a biofilter for microbial maturation (MMS), and a recirculating aquaculture system (RAS). Sources of bacteria in the rearing tank included external sources of bacteria (i.e., incoming water, microalgae, and live feed) and growth of bacteria in the rearing tanks. Our results supported that careful preparation and manipulation of the initial bacterial community can improve rearing conditions, particularly in FTS and MMS, by impacting the initial colonization. A lower bacterial carrying capacity in the inflowing water compared to the tank water was a challenge in FTS and MMS, as the increased access to organic matter led to substantial internal growth of bacteria in the rearing tank. Bacterial production within the rearing tank relative to incoming bacteria from water was measured to be 89 % and 94 % in FTS and MMS, respectively, compared to 49 % in RAS. Quantitatively, the live feed was the dominant source of bacteria to the larval gut (>95 %). The uptake of bacteria by larvae from the rearing water was higher in RAS (3.28 %) than in FTS (0.86 %) and MMS (0.75 %). Although the live feed microbiota dominated the number of microbes entering the gut in this study, previous research has shown that the microbial composition of the larval gut generally has higher similarity to the rearing water than to the bacteria associated with the live feed. This can be explained by the selection pressure created in/by the host. Our results also showed that biofilters significantly affected bacterial composition and density by enhancing microbial richness and evenness in the water. Depending on the organic matter load, biofilters release substantial numbers of bacteria into the water, potentially structuring the microbial environment for larvae. The microbial influence of biofilters has been shown in previous studies to enhance larval survival, i.e. higher survival in RAS and MMS compared to FTS. However, more research is necessary to explain the specific role that bacterial communities play in promoting larval health and survival. This study is the first attempt to make a bacterial budget for various larval-rearing systems. It shows that rearing technology has a tremendous impact on the microbial quality that the reared larvae are exposed to, and this new knowledge can be used to develop microbial management strategies.

1. Introduction

The production of high-quality juveniles remains a major bottleneck in the aquaculture of many species of fish, crustaceans, and shellfish

(Langangen et al., 2014; Richards et al., 2015; Dubert et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2022). The symptoms of poor performance include poor appetite, slow growth, low survival, and poor stress coping. This is a problem for many species in an early stage of commercial production, as only 10–15

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% manage to survive the larval stage (Vadstein et al., 2018b; Vadstein et al., 2013). Detrimental fish-microbe interactions are the main cause of the poor performance of larvae (Attramadal et al., 2014; Leyton et al., 2017; Vadstein et al., 2018b; Vadstein et al., 2004). This emphasizes the necessity of developing strategies to promote positive interactions (Vadstein et al., 2018a; Vadstein et al., 2013).

The bacterial density and community composition to which larvae are exposed in marine hatcheries depend on multiple factors, including the number and types of bacteria transported in from different external sources and the selection pressure controlling bacterial growth and loss rates in the system. The selection pressure and transport of bacteria are affected by factors like organic matter supply, disinfection, and water exchange rates (Vadstein et al., 2018a, 2018b). Changes in the rearing regime, e.g., increasing water exchange rates and feeding, influence the conditions of the bacteria in the system by altering the transport of bacteria and/or the supply of organic matter. External sources of bacteria include incoming water, air, bacteria associated with eggs/fish, live feed, and microalgae. Internal fluxes, production, and selection of bacteria within the rearing tanks differ between habitats, like the biofilm on surfaces, the water volume, the larvae, and the live feed (Burns et al., 2016; Schoina et al., 2022). Further, different rearing system designs include different treatment steps and solutions that affect the bacteria, like water reuse, biofiltration, and disinfection (Attramadal et al., 2014; Attramadal et al., 2012a).

A typical marine rearing system involves complex dynamics for bacteria in different habitats (Fig. 1). In a rearing tank, there is an exchange of bacteria between the wall biofilm and water microbiota, and larvae, live feed, and microalgae have their associated microbiota. The exchange of bacteria between different organisms and between the water and organisms in the rearing tank includes predation, drinking behaviour and defecation (Fig. 1). The high number of microbial species and the food web make the first feeding rearing tank a complex ecosystem with many interactions (Bakke et al., 2015; Giatsis et al., 2014). Fig. 1 also indicates the typical variations in the structural and operational attributes of different rearing systems, characterized by the options of recirculation of water and the inclusion of biofilters and disinfection. There is so far limited understanding regarding the contributions from different bacterial habitats to the abundance and composition of bacterial communities within larvae-rearing water and its dependence on rearing systems configuration. Additionally, the uptake of bacteria by the larvae could play a crucial role in determining

their viability. However, there is limited knowledge concerning the uptake of bacteria from the rearing water and live feed through drinking and feeding.

Heterotrophic bacteria dominate in intensive rearing systems (Gonzalez-Silva et al., 2016; Rurangwa and Verdegem, 2015). In general, the limiting factor for the growth of heterotrophic bacteria in aquaculture systems is the supply of organic matter, which thus determines the bacterial carrying capacity of the system. Compared to the sea or natural conditions, closed production systems with high biomass and feeding offer a high supply of organic matter, which supports relatively high densities of heterotrophic bacteria (Vadstein et al., 2013). The supply of organic matter typically increases over the production cycle due to the growth of cultured organisms and the associated increase in feeding and waste production. Larvae may require different types of live and formulated feed and/or supply of other additives like microalgae at various stages of production. These requirements change often due to the rapid growth of the larvae, including increasing mouth size and development of the digestive system. The supply of organic matter may also vary over the day according to the light regime and variable feed supply (Navarro-Guillén et al., 2023).

The potential for the growth of bacteria in the water of the rearing tank is strongly dependent on the hydraulic retention time (HRT) (Dahle et al., 2022; Vadstein et al., 2018a). Fast-growing bacteria have doubling times of an hour or even less (Gibson et al., 2018). The water exchange rates of tanks in marine hatcheries are relatively low during the first weeks (i.e., typical HRT of 1–8 h) to protect larvae from mechanical stress and to reduce the dilution of costly live feed from the tanks. A longer HRT in the rearing tanks provides additional time for bacterial growth in the water volume and accumulation of waste products like CO₂ and ammonia. In comparison, the HRT is shorter for larger fish tanks, often under 1 h, to transport waste compounds and bacteria rapidly out of the rearing tank (Bakke et al., 2017; Dahle et al., 2022). A shorter HRT in the rearing tanks results in limited bacterial growth within the tank water volume. There is a lack of knowledge regarding the contribution of the internal growth of bacteria within rearing tanks, which could be an important factor in determining the overall abundance and composition of bacterial communities in the rearing water.

On the rearing system level, the water dilution rate in recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) is, per definition, much lower than in flow-through systems (FTS) and microbially matured systems (MMS), which is a FTS with a biofilter on the intake water (Fig. 2). Due to the

Fig. 1. This figure illustrates and structures the complex dynamics of bacteria in different habitats during larval first feeding in an aquaculture rearing system. Key elements include the formation and uptake of dissolved organic matter (DOM), bacterial sources (internal and external), and feeding routes involving live feed and microalgae with associated microbiota. Arrows denote the direction of effects. Interactions among bacterial species are not shown. “+/-” symbols show important variations in system design, which may or may not include recirculation of water, biofilter and/or disinfection that impact the quality and quantity of bacteria entering the tank. This figure was created with [BioRender.com](https://www.biorender.com) with agreement number TY273FDZ17.

Fig. 2. Conceptual set-up of the three different rearing systems: the flow-through system (FTS), the microbially matured system (MMS) and the recirculating aquaculture system (RAS). The width of the arrow is an indication of the water flow rate.

high degree of water reuse, RAS has a system HRT of days to weeks, whereas, in comparison, FTS and MMS have a system HRT in the order of hours. An important effect of a longer water retention time in the system (i.e., RAS) is that it allows slow-growing mobile bacteria (i.e., planktonic and on particles in the water volume) to remain in the system. Conditions that favour slow-growing specialist bacteria, such as the stable supply of organic matter and low system dilution rates, benefit marine fish larvae (Attramadal et al., 2014; Bakke et al., 2017). There is a limited understanding of the relative and absolute contributions of bacteria from incoming water and internal growth within the rearing tanks of different rearing systems.

Point disinfection methods, e.g., UV treatment, where the disinfection effect does not follow the water flow, result in a temporary reduction in the number of bacteria. However, the bacterial carrying capacity influenced by substrate availability remains unaffected. Consequently, there is rapid bacterial regrowth within the system following disinfection (Attramadal et al., 2012a; Hess-Erga et al., 2010). Likewise, adding chemical disinfectants that follow the water for some time through the system influences the conditions for bacteria growth (Pedersen et al., 2010). Sessile populations in biofilms have lower susceptibility to disinfection than the suspended populations due to the protective nature of the biofilm matrix (Bridier et al., 2011; Li et al., 2021).

Compared to FTS, a key feature of the MMS and RAS is the inclusion of a large area available for biofilm growth in the biofilter. The biofilter facilitates organic matter degradation and increases competition for limited resources for bacterial growth over time. Strong competition for the available organic matter in the biofilter develops because the biomass builds up to match the supply of organic matter. This secures a more K-selected and stable community and selection for slow-growing, beneficial bacteria in the water entering the rearing tanks (Attramadal et al., 2014). Depending on the system design, the water leaving the biofilter in MMS and RAS may pass through other treatment units but always ends up in the fish tanks. Knowledge of how the communities of the biofilter biofilm affect the density and composition of the rearing water microbiota is poorly understood.

This study aimed to comprehensively understand bacterial dynamics in land-based aquaculture systems and focused on which factors affect the bacteria the larvae are exposed to. The study included three main

objectives:

Estimate and compare the influence of external sources of bacteria (i.e., intake water, microalgae, and live feed) with the internal growth of bacteria in the rearing tanks and hence in the immediate surroundings of the larvae. Three distinct rearing system designs were compared: RAS, MMS, and FTS.

Quantify and compare the uptake of bacteria by larvae through drinking and feeding over time in the same three system designs.

Investigate how biofilm communities affect the bacterial density and community composition of the water by considering the effects of biofilm surface-to-water volume ratio, the dilution rate of the biofilter reactor, temperature, and nutrient loading.

The work for objectives 1 and 2 was based on a theoretical approach (collection, reanalysis and simulation using a spreadsheet of previously unpublished data from Attramadal et al. (2014) as well as published data from Attramadal et al. (2014), Olsen et al. (2000), Salvesen et al. (1999), and Skjermo and Vadstein (1993)). The work on objective 3 was based on an experimental approach comprised of lab experiments with biofilter reactors.

2. Materials and methods

A theoretical approach was followed to address the first and second objectives. In this approach, data were collected, systematized, re-analyzed, and simulated using a spreadsheet. The quantitative and qualitative influences from different sources on rearing water microbial communities in three distinct land-based rearing systems—FTS, MMS, and RAS—were investigated for comparable conditions. Our rearing system designs were similar to those used by Attramadal et al. (2014), as we primarily utilized data from their study to make general predictions relevant to the three rearing systems. The data for the number of bacteria in rearing tank water and the incoming water to rearing tanks were from Attramadal et al. (2014), where it had been determined by flow cytometry (FAC-Scan Becton Dickinson, UK). To quantify bacteria proliferating within the fish tanks (internal growth) in our study, we utilized data obtained by measuring the incorporation of radioactively labelled leucine from the same study (Attramadal et al., 2014). The number of live feed and microalgae used was based on the Attramadal et al. (2014), and the bacteria per live feed and microalgae were derived from relevant literature (Olsen et al., 2000; Salvesen et al., 1999; Skjermo and Vadstein, 1993). A spreadsheet model based on data from Attramadal et al. (2014) was developed to calculate live feed ingestion per Atlantic cod larva at various days post-hatching (dph). Bacterial ingestion with live feed was calculated by multiplying the number of live feed ingested (as derived from the spreadsheet model) by the number of bacteria per live feed (based on relevant literature) (Olsen et al., 2000; Skjermo and Vadstein, 1993). To estimate bacterial uptake from rearing water, an exponential model—based on drinking rates of Atlantic cod larvae—was applied to published data (Mangor-Jensen and Adoff, 1987; Tytler and Blaxter, 1988), and uptake rates were derived by multiplying the drinking rate by 100 (Reitan et al., 1998). To address the third objective, experiments were conducted using bioreactors to investigate the impact of biofilter biofilm on water microbiota.

2.1. Bacterial flows to and production within tanks in different rearing systems

To assess bacterial contributions in different rearing systems, we analyzed bacterial loads across three distinct rearing setups: FTS, MMS, and RAS. This analysis enabled a comparison of bacterial contributions from various sources and an assessment of how different system configurations impacted the microbiota in rearing tanks.

2.1.1. Input data for estimation of bacterial loads in water flows

Data from an experiment with Atlantic cod reared in three distinct rearing systems (FTS, MMS and RAS) (Attramadal et al., 2014) were used to estimate bacterial loads in water flows for each rearing regime. The general concept designs of the systems are shown in Fig. 2. The intake (new) water is filtered and disinfected for all systems when entering the system. In the MMS, the disinfected intake water is treated in an aerobic biofilter that secures recolonisation of the water before water goes to the rearing tanks (Attramadal et al., 2016; Attramadal et al., 2014; Attramadal et al., 2012b; Salvesen et al., 1999; Skjermo et al., 1997). In both FTS and MMS, the water is led in a single pass through the rearing tanks, and no water is reused. In RAS, less intake water (disinfected new makeup water) is used, and water from the fish tanks is reused after solids removal, aerobic biofiltration, and degassing (Blancheton et al., 2013; Martins et al., 2010).

Our analysis was performed for conditions and feeding regime representative for the rearing of Atlantic cod larvae over an observation window of 3 to 30 dph (Attramadal et al., 2014). Various rearing conditions were considered according to typical larval rearing practices, including increasing tank water exchange rates of 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 tank volumes per day, changed in steps at 5, 11, 16, and 22 dph, respectively. These rearing conditions were made consistent for three different rearing systems. Our calculations considered a feeding regime typically applied to the rearing of cod larvae, consistent across three different rearing systems (Attramadal et al., 2014). Rotifers were fed daily from 3 to 21 dph and then with *Artemia* from 22 to 30 dph.

Input data for bacterial densities from different sources (introduced with the live feed and the water coming into the tanks) are shown in Table 1. The data for bacterial densities in the incoming water to the rearing tank were derived from Attramadal et al. (2014). Incoming water refers to the water entering the larvae-rearing tanks of all three rearing systems. It should not be confused with the intake or makeup water to the systems. Before entering the rearing tanks, the water undergoes treatment with a biofilter in both MMS and RAS, but it is only recirculated in the case of RAS (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2). In the study by Attramadal et al. (2014), the densities of bacteria in incoming water to rearing tanks were tenfold higher in the RAS compared to the other systems and about double in the FTS compared to the MMS. The spreadsheet used to estimate the densities of bacteria in the incoming water to the rearing tanks is shared in the supplementary file (Supplementary file 1: sheets 1.1 and 1.2).

To compare the contributions from the different sources of bacteria under typical initial conditions, the bacterial contributions from the live feed (5000 rotifers L⁻¹) and microalgae (1.3 × 10⁸ cells L⁻¹) just before

Table 1

Bacterial numbers estimated for external bacteria sources for three different marine larviculture systems, including the bacteria numbers estimated in the incoming water to rearing tanks, in the live feed when fed to the tanks and in the microalgae cultures added to tanks.

Aquaculture systems	Representative number of bacterial cells from inlet water to fish tanks	References
FTS	0.2 × 10 ⁶ mL ⁻¹	(Attramadal et al., 2014)
MMS	0.1 × 10 ⁶ mL ⁻¹	(Attramadal et al., 2014)
RAS	2.5 × 10 ⁶ mL ⁻¹	(Attramadal et al., 2014)
Live feed/algae	Representative number of bacterial cells from added live feed	
Rotifers	10 ⁴ per rotifer	(Skjermo and Vadstein, 1993)
<i>Artemia</i>	2 × 10 ⁵ per <i>Artemia</i>	(Olsen et al., 2000)
Microalgae culture	4 per algae cell	(Salvesen et al., 1999)

the addition to fish tanks (Table 1 and materials and methods: 2.1.3) were calculated for stagnant conditions in the fish tank, i.e. no water exchange. The initial bacterial concentration in the tank water was determined from the number of bacteria in the incoming water for the rearing system, e.g. the tanks were filled with the incoming water going to the tanks for the relevant system with no or limited subsequent time for internal growth of bacteria (Table 1). The initial concentration of bacteria in the tank water was then calculated for the three systems (Supplementary file 1: sheet 1.7).

2.1.2. Input data for estimating the internal production of bacteria

To estimate bacterial growth within rearing systems, we used data from Attramadal et al. (2014) as input. In their study, the production of heterotrophic bacterial biomass was measured in water samples from three different systems by incorporating radioactively labelled ³H-Leucine into macromolecules (protein biosynthesis) (Kirchman, 1993). The number of bacteria produced within the system was calculated from the incorporated ³H-leucine, assuming 30 fg C cell⁻¹ (Fukuda et al., 1998; Troussellier et al., 1997). The loss of bacteria from the rearing tank due to dilution can be calculated from the concentration of bacteria in the rearing water and the tank water exchange rate, but this is not presented here. The calculations of the internal growth of the bacteria within the rearing tanks are shown in a spreadsheet (Supplementary file 1: sheet 1.3).

2.1.3. Input data for the estimation of bacterial contribution from the live feed

We estimated the bacterial load introduced by live feed sources, specifically microalgae, rotifers, and *Artemia*, into rearing tanks. This approach aimed to assess the relative impact of live feed microbiota on the overall microbial density in rearing water. Given the variable nature of bacterial densities associated with live feed, we focused on representative population estimates to make meaningful comparisons between bacterial contributions across different rearing systems and feed types.

For simplicity, it was assumed that all bacteria coming into the rearing tanks with the live feed influenced the microbial density of the tank water. However, this will not be the case, as much of the live feed is ingested by larvae or diluted from the tank before the gut microbes of the feed organisms are completely exchanged with the rearing water. For example, *Artemia franciscana* was shown to exchange most of the gut microbiota in 4 h when grazing on live microalgae at 20 °C (Olsen et al., 2000). In the presented simulation, the influence of the feed microbiota on the bacterial density of the rearing water is, therefore, a theoretical maximum and likely an overestimation.

The bacterial load coming with the live feed, including microalgae, rotifers, and *Artemia*, is variable and dependent on the cultivation methods and the washing procedures used. Since it is hard to determine correct numbers of general value, the primary focus of this study was to select representative orders of magnitude for the bacterial populations that can be realistically expected in the different sources for our calculations. By adopting this approach, we aimed to facilitate the investigation and comparison of the relative influence between different systems and situations despite the uncertainty of accurate numerical values. Skjermo and Vadstein (1993) reported that rotifers had 3.6 × 10³ CFU (colony-forming units, i.e., culturable bacteria) per individual (n = 9). In the same experiment, culturable bacteria in rotifer culture water averaged 5.7 ± 6.8 % of the total number of bacteria counted in the microscope. Using the same factor (5.7 %) to calculate the total number of bacteria from CFU associated with the rotifers gives 6.4 × 10⁴ bacteria per individual rotifer. Data from Øie et al. (1994) showed that CFU per rotifer could be lower, as rotifers cultured on live algae had only 77–140 CFU per individual. Therefore, a relevant estimation for our calculations was 10⁴ bacteria per rotifer (Table 1). Olsen et al. (2000) reported that a typical 2-day-old *A. franciscana* had 2.4 × 10⁴ CFU per individual. Using the same factor to calculate the total number of

bacteria from CFU as used for the rotifers (culturable bacteria 5.7 ± 6.8 % of the total) gives an estimate of 2×10^5 bacteria per individual *Artemia* (Table 1).

Typically, but not always, microalgae (as live culture or algae paste) are added from the start and along with the feeding of rotifers (in the case of Atlantic cod in Attramadal et al. (2014) until 21 dph). The bacterial densities vary greatly in algal cultures (Salvesen et al., 1999). For this analysis, the protocol described in Attramadal et al. (2014) was followed, assuming an initial addition of 1 mg C L^{-1} of *Isochrysis galbana* for “green water,” which corresponds to a concentration of 1.3×10^5 cells mL^{-1} in the rearing tank (Reitan et al., 1993). A normal density for an algae culture at harvest is typically 10^7 cells mL^{-1} of *I. galbana* (Reitan et al., 1993). According to Salvesen et al. (1999), the total bacteria counts associated with the algae cultures (including *I. galbana*) varied between 1.7×10^7 and 4.0×10^7 bacteria mL^{-1} . Therefore, in this analysis, an estimate was made assuming that the algae culture addition contributes 4 bacteria per algae cell to the rearing tanks (Table 1). This addition of microalgae was included in the current study to illustrate the likely level of impact, but was omitted from further discussion regarding the various sources of bacteria at post-start-up due to the considerable variation associated with the bacterial quantities introduced with each volume of algal culture (depending on the algal cultivation form, density, growth rate and the species (Salvesen et al., 1999)).

2.2. Input data for consumption of bacteria from live feed and rearing water by larvae

To assess bacterial ingestion with live feed by fish larvae, we developed a spreadsheet model based on data from Attramadal et al. (2014) (Supplementary file 1: sheet 1.5, and sheet 1.6). The model was used to simulate daily growth and survival rates from 3 to 30 dph, connecting the nutrient content of live feed and ensuring the optimal development of Atlantic cod larvae. The simulation used an initial stocking density of 100 larvae L^{-1} and anticipated a 30 % survival rate at 30 dph, assuming a biomass yield of 20 %. This spreadsheet facilitated the determination of the consumption of live feed per larva. Subsequently, the consumption of bacteria associated with live feed was calculated using data in Table 1 (see also materials and methods: 2.1.3.). The calculations are shown in Supplementary file 1: sheet 1.1 and sheet 1.2.

To determine the uptake rate of bacteria from the rearing water by larvae, we used previous estimates for the drinking rates of larvae. An exponential model was fitted to published data for Atlantic cod (1–7 dph; (Mangor-Jensen and Adoff, 1987); 19 dph, (Tytler and Blaxter, 1988): Drinking rate ($\text{nL larvae}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$) = $1.08e^{0.168 \cdot \text{age}}$, age in dph, $R^2 = 0.99$; see Supplementary file 1: sheet 1.1, sheet 1.2, sheet 1.4, and Supplementary file 2: supplementary fig. 1). The uptake rate of bacteria was assumed to be 100 times the drinking rate, as suggested by (Reitan et al., 1998). The uptake rates of bacteria from the water by larvae across the three distinct rearing systems (FTS, MMS, and RAS) were calculated by multiplying the bacterial density of the rearing water (calculated based on Attramadal et al. (2014)) with the drinking rate multiplied by 100, and the uptake by the cod population was calculated as the uptake rate by an individual multiplied by population density.

2.3. Biofilter-biofilm communities' effects on the densities and composition of bacteria in the water leaving the biofilter

2.3.1. Effects of the dilution rate of the bioreactor and the biofilter biofilm on the number and composition of planktonic bacteria in the water leaving the biofilter

To investigate how the biofilter biofilm and dilution rate of the bioreactor affect the number of planktonic bacteria in the water leaving the bioreactor, a 56-day Experiment 2.1 was conducted with reactors at 12 and 20 °C (controlled with a water bath), respectively (Supplementary file 2: supplementary fig. 2). We selected 12 °C to simulate

typical aquaculture conditions for cold-water species like Atlantic cod and salmon, and 20 °C to observe microbial shifts at a warmer temperature. This comparison helps to assess biofilter resilience under potential temperature fluctuations and dilution rates in aquaculture. For each of the two temperatures, the experiment involved one continuous reactor containing seawater (300 mL) and matured biofilm carriers with a total effective surface area of 662 cm^2 (AnoxKaldnes K1 MBBR with an effective surface area of 4.9 cm^2 per carrier (Ødegaard et al., 2000), see Supplementary file 2: A7. supplementary table 1). These matured biofilm carriers originated from a biofilter kept at NTNU Centre for Fisheries and Aquaculture, Brattørkaia, Trondheim, Norway. Additionally, one continuous reactor was run with only seawater as a biofilter-free control for each temperature. Seawater M65 medium (Supplementary file 2: see A8. supplementary table 2) was used to feed all reactors, and the flow rate was initially set at 12.5 mL/h, equal to a dilution rate of one reactor volume per day (HRT of 24 h). The purpose of using seawater M65 medium, in general, is to provide a nutritionally balanced, nutrient-rich marine environment suitable for bacterial growth in both the water phase and the biofilm. The dilution rate was increased stepwise: from an initial dilution of 1 d^{-1} (HRT of 24 h for 15 days) to one volume exchanged every 0.47 d^{-1} (11.3 h HRT for 21 days), one volume exchanged every 0.21 d^{-1} (5 h HRT for 14 days), and finally one volume exchanged every 0.1 d^{-1} (HRT of 2.4 h for 6 days). Measurement of pH and salinity was performed weekly. BD Accuri C6 Flow Cytometer (BD Bioscience, San Jose) was used to count bacterial cells in water samples collected from each of the four reactors. Additionally, for contamination assessment, cell count analyses were performed on samples from the water source and M65 media stock used, both before autoclaving and after use in the reactors. The set-up of bioreactors and additional information on the experiments are presented in Supplementary file 2: supplementary fig. 2.

2.3.2. Quantification of release of bacteria from biofilm to water

To quantify the release of bacteria from the biofilm, biofilm carriers collected at the end of Experiment 2.1 were used for a subsequent 4-h experiment (Experiment 2.3) (Supplementary file 2: supplementary fig. 2). In addition, Experiment 2.2 was performed to quantify the release of bacteria in Experiment 2.3 from biofilm on carriers that had been consecutively treated at two different levels of organic loading at room temperature (Supplementary file 2: supplementary fig. 3). Specifically, for the low nutrient treatment, a dose of 55 μL of seawater M65 medium was added to the reactor (5 L water, 1 L carriers) three days a week (Monday, Wednesday, and Friday) for 106 days. After 106 days, biofilm carriers representing the low-nutrient treatment were collected for the first release experiment (Experiment 2.3). After the first release experiment, the biofilm carriers used in the experiment were returned to the same reactor treated with low nutrients in Experiment 2.2. All carriers in the same bioreactor were then exposed to a high-nutrient treatment for the next 84 days. For the high-nutrient treatment, a dose of 165 μL of M65 medium was added to the reactor three days a week (Monday, Wednesday, and Friday) for 84 days. After 84 days, the biofilm carriers representing the high-nutrient treatment were collected for the second release experiment (Experiment 2.3). The original concentration of the seawater M65 medium stock used was 150 g/L. The medium used during incubation was sterile filtered through 0.2 μm filters and autoclaved. Seawater was added as needed to balance the loss of water by evaporation. The water was exchanged every week, and seawater was added to correct for evaporation for the previous days.

Biofilm carriers from two of the experiments described above (Experiment 2.1: high and low temperature, and Experiment 2.2: high and low nutrient loading) were used in Experiment 2.3 immersed in particle-free seawater in separate bioreactors, with magnetic stirring, sterile aeration and incubated at the temperatures corresponding with the temperatures to which the respective carriers had been previously exposed (Supplementary file 2: supplementary fig. 4). The carriers underwent a single gentle rinse in particle-free seawater before

transferring to reactors. Autoclaved 500 mL reactors were filled with 300 mL of particle-free seawater and the respective carriers with a total effective surface area of 588 cm². To assess cell release rates, water samples were collected from the reactors at intervals: first prior to carrier introduction (zero sample), then immediately following carrier addition after allowing them to mix with seawater for a few minutes, and then subsequently at 0.5-h intervals for the next 4 h. For each water sample, 495 µL was combined with 5 µL of glutaraldehyde (50 %) to a final concentration of 0.5 %, incubated for 15 min at room temperature and promptly frozen in liquid nitrogen. Samples were also collected from each medium container to confirm sterility. All samples were stored in a freezer set at -20 °C. The samples were analyzed by BD Accuri C6 Flow Cytometer (BD Bioscience, San Jose). Details of the procedure for flowcytometry are given in **Supplementary file 2: A6**.

To determine the number of bacterial cells released from matured carriers in Experiment 2.3, we calculated the release rate (cells cm⁻² h⁻¹) by dividing the cells per µL (from flow cytometry) by the total effective surface area of the biofilm carriers (cm²) and time (h). The volume of water supplied (µL) per cm² of effective biofilm surface area was calculated by dividing the total water volume by the total effective surface area of the biofilm carriers used in the reactors. The release percentage was determined by dividing the release rate (cells cm⁻² h⁻¹) by the total biofilm cells cm⁻². To calculate the total biofilm cells cm⁻², we measured the total biofilm cDNA concentration per carrier and the ng DNA per bacterial cell (based on cDNA concentration in water divided by bacterial cells per µL in water, and the water used was sterile and particle-free before the introduction of biofilm carriers). The cDNA was used instead of DNA to detect active microbial communities in the biofilm and water, as cDNA reflects the actively transcribed 16S rRNA genes. The concentration of cDNA was measured using the Invitrogen™ Qubit™ 3 Fluorometer, while bacterial cells in water were quantified using BD Accuri C6 Flow Cytometer (BD Bioscience, San Jose).

2.3.3. Effects of the surface area of biofilter biofilm on the number of planktonic bacteria

Experiment 2.4 was carried out to determine the influence of relative surface area per water volume of biofilm on the number of planktonic bacteria (**Supplementary file 2: supplementary fig. 5**). Lab-scale continuous reactors (0.5 L) were filled with either biofilm carriers containing active biofilm communities (with an effective surface area of 4.9 cm² per carrier (Ødegaard et al., 2000)) to an effective surface area of 343 cm² (Low surface area treatment) or 666 cm² (High surface area treatment) and growth medium (250 mL of seawater and 50 mL of seawater M65 medium (Supplementary Table 1)). The total effective surface area and filling degree for the high surface area treatment were aligned with those commonly used and recommended in RAS, while for the low surface area treatment, the filling degree was reduced to half of that to investigate its comparative impact on planktonic bacterial load. Three replicate reactors were operated for each treatment. The reactors received air and medium through the same inlet tube, while culture and air were discharged through the outlet. A dilution rate was maintained consistent with the flow rate of 0.937 mL/min, equivalent to two volumes exchanged per day (12 h HRT), and a temperature of 18 °C was maintained throughout the experiment. The experiment was run for 84 days, with samples collected weekly. The configuration of bioreactors and additional experimental information are shown in **Supplementary file 2: supplementary fig. 5**.

2.3.4. Assessment of the bacterial communities

To assess bacterial community composition in water from reactors with and without biofilm carriers (Experiment 2.1), 50–65 mL of water was sampled. Similarly, the same volume of water was sampled at the end of Experiment 2.3 to examine variations in bacterial community composition among biofilm, water, and released particles, and to understand how different nutrient loadings can influence these communities. In Experiment 2.1, bacterial communities from water samples

were directly collected using sterile 0.2 µm hollow fibre syringe filters (2.5 cm²) (DynaGard, Microgon Inc., California) and stored at -80 °C. In Experiment 2.3, both particle-associated and planktonic bacterial communities were collected. To capture larger particle-associated bacterial communities, 50–65 mL water was measured with a cylinder and initially filtered through a 3.0 µm, 47 mm polycarbonate filter (Whatman Cyclopore, Maidstone). The filtrate was then filtered through a 0.2 µm, 47 mm polycarbonate filter (Whatman Cyclopore, Maidstone) to collect the fraction containing freely suspended bacterial cells. Both collected filters were placed in cryotubes and stored at -80 °C. Biofilm carriers from experiments (Experiments 2.1 and 2.3) were collected from reactors and preserved at -80 °C.

Samples from Experiments 2.1 and 2.3 were subjected to DNA extraction using the Power Soil DNA Isolation Kit (MOBIO) as described by the manufacturers. Variable regions 3 and 4 of the bacterial 16S rRNA gene were amplified by using the primers Ill-338F (5-ctactcgggwgccag-cag) and Ill-805R (5-gactacnvgggtatctaakcc) as described in Nordgård et al. (2017). The resulting PCR products were purified, normalized, and indexed as described in Nordgård et al. (2017). The final amplicon library included 95 samples that were sequenced at the Norwegian Sequencing Center in one MiSeq run using v3 reagents and paired-end sequencing. The resulting sequencing data was deposited at the European Nucleotide Archive (accession number: ERS20902157-ERS20902251). The Usearch pipeline (version 9.2) was used to process the amplicon sequencing data (USEARCH manual (drive5.com)). The command “merge_pairs” was used to merge forward and reverse reads, trim off primer sequences, and discard merged sequences shorter than 380 bp (base pairs). The merged sequences were quality filtered using the command “fastq_filter” with an expected error threshold of 1. OTU (operational taxonomic unit) clustering at the 97 % similarity level was performed using the command “cluster_otus” (Edgar, 2013). Taxonomy assignment was performed by using the “sintax” command with the RDP reference data set (version 15). Finally, an OTU table was made using the command “otutab”.

2.4. Data analysis

The data analyses for enumerating and visualization of bacterial cell numbers were executed using R software (<https://cran.r-project.org/mirrors.html>, version 4.4.0) and MS Excel (<https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoft-365/excel>, version 2405). In the bioreactor experiment (Experiment 2.1), analyses for microbial community composition and statistics were conducted in R software (version 4.4.0) using the packages Phyloseq (version 1.42.0) and Vegan (version 2.6–4). Prior to inferential tests, the normality assumption of the data was assessed via the Shapiro-Wilk test (shapiro.test function). To investigate group differences for normally distributed data, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used. Alternatively, when the data deviated from normality, the Wilcoxon rank sum (wilcox.test function) was applied for two-group comparisons, while the Kruskal-Wallis test (kruskal.test function) was used for multiple comparisons. OTU tables were used to generate principal coordinate analyses (PCoAs) using the ordinate function from phyloseq for Bray-Curtis similarities. Both two-way and one-way PEMAANOVA (permutational multivariate analysis of variance) tests based on Bray-Curtis similarities were done using the adonis2 function from vegan package (version 2.6–4) by running it with 9999 permutations and without square of distances in R software (Anderson et al., 2008; Anderson, 2001). These tests were used to assess bacterial community composition variation between samples with sufficient replicates. Alpha diversity was evaluated as Hill numbers (Hill, 1973; Kindt et al., 2006; Tóthmérész, 1995) with the reyni function from the vegan package. Venn diagrams were created using Eulerr packages (version 7.0.2). The ggplot2 package (version 3.5.1) was used to create bar plots and boxplots. In the bioreactor experiment (Experiment 2.3), NMDS (non-metric multidimensional scaling) (Taguchi and Oono, 2005) was used to perform ordinations based on Bray-Curtis similarities (see

Attramadal et al. (2014) for further details).

3. Results

3.1. Bacterial sources and flows to and production within tanks in different rearing systems

3.1.1. Initial conditions and the effect of adding microalgae to the rearing water

To compare the contributions of bacteria from different sources under typical initial conditions, we calculated the bacterial inputs from live feed (5000 rotifers L^{-1}), microalgae (1.3×10^8 cells L^{-1}), and incoming water to the rearing tanks of three different rearing systems (Table 1 and materials and methods: 2.1.1 and 2.1.3). These calculations were done just before their addition to the larval rearing tanks, assuming stagnant conditions with no water exchange. Our results showed that, in RAS, the water used to fill the tanks was the dominant source of bacteria (Fig. 3). For FTS and MMS, the addition of microalgae contributed 2.6 and 5.2 times more than the filling water, respectively. Adding microalgae, thus, greatly influenced both MMS and FTS more than the RAS. The bacteria supplied with the initial feeding of live feed was of minor importance for all rearing systems.

3.1.2. Bacterial contribution due to the release of organic substrate during hatching

The fish eggs are also an initial source of bacteria and nutrients if the hatching occurs in the rearing tanks. Eggs are commonly surface-disinfected before hatching (Salvesen and Vadstein, 1995). However, during hatching, a significant pulse of organic substrate is released (around 20–25 % of total egg carbon for turbot, unpublished data). With a stocking density of 100 eggs L^{-1} in our study, this could correspond to a release of around 700 μg C L^{-1} during hatching. This can potentially increase the bacterial density of roughly 10^9 cells L^{-1} , assuming a growth yield of 21 % and 20 fg C cell $^{-1}$ (Bjørnsen, 1986; Lee and Fuhrman, 1987). This could correspond to a substantial theoretical increase of around 3 to 11 times in cell density. The calculations are shown in the Supplementary_file_1: sheet_1.8.

3.1.3. Bacterial contribution due to organic substrate from dead larvae and uneaten feed

Dead fish larvae not removed from the rearing tanks decompose and supply organic substrate for bacteria. This is particularly important to consider during the initial phases of larval development when the mortality of fish larvae is typically high and dead larvae are difficult to remove before they disintegrate and without disturbing the living larvae. To investigate this issue, we estimated the mean dry weight of the dead Atlantic cod larvae for selected timepoints. We used unpublished data from Attramadal et al. (2014) to calculate the dry mass of dead larvae, and timepoints were selected to establish conditions comparable to those of other analyses. From these calculations, we found that for 4, 9, 17 and 30 dph, the mean dry mass contribution from dead larvae can be in the magnitude of 0.57, 0.14, 0.17, and 0.27 mg DW L^{-1} day $^{-1}$, respectively. The dead, uneaten live feed may also be a source of organic matter release in the rearing tank. We did not estimate the possible production of bacteria due to this supply of organic matter.

3.1.4. Estimation of relative contributions of bacteria from incoming water and live feed to the bacterial density of the rearing tanks

We further estimated the quantitative contributions from different sources of bacteria to the bacterial density of rearing water during the rotifer and the *Artemia* feeding phase (Fig. 4). The data for bacterial contribution from the water was obtained from Attramadal et al. (2014), while the data for bacterial contribution from live feed was derived from (Attramadal et al., 2014; Olsen et al., 2000; Skjermo and Vadstein, 1993) (Table 1, and materials and methods: 2.1.3).

During the rotifer feeding phase, we found that the incoming water was the dominant source of bacteria in all systems (75 ± 7 %, 64 ± 12 %, and 97 ± 2 % in FTS, MMS, and RAS, respectively) when compared to the live feed (Fig. 4). During the *Artemia* phase, however, the live feed was found to be the most important source of bacteria in the FTS (77 ± 11 %) and MMS (87 ± 8 %). In contrast, RAS had the lowest bacterial contribution from live feed (20 ± 6 %), as the incoming water remained the predominant source of bacteria for this system (80 ± 6 %).

3.1.5. Comparison between the incoming bacteria and the internal production of planktonic bacteria in the rearing tanks

In all rearing systems, bacterial production within the rearing tank

Fig. 3. Estimated contributions from different bacterial sources on the initial bacterial densities in the water volume of larvae rearing tank following the addition of water, microalgae, and live feed on the first day for a stocking density of 100 larvae L^{-1} in three different rearing systems: FTS, MMS and RAS. This is based on an initial addition of 5000 rotifers L^{-1} and 1.3×10^8 cells of microalgae L^{-1} .

Fig. 4. Estimated relative supply of bacteria coming in with water and live feed to larvae rearing tanks with production time in the three different rearing systems: FTS, MMS, and RAS during the first 30 days post-hatching (dph). The data are also categorised by the different tank dilution rates on the top of the panel (D, tank volume exchanged per day, d^{-1}). In our calculations, the rotifer period was from day 3 to day 21. After that *Artemia* was the live food.

relative to incoming bacteria was estimated to be a major source of bacteria (89 %, 94 % and 49 % for FTS, MMS, and RAS, respectively, Fig. 5a). Internally produced bacteria amounted to $69 \times 10^8 \pm 16 \times 10^8$, $63 \times 10^8 \pm 14 \times 10^8$, and $115 \times 10^8 \pm 18 \times 10^8$ cells $L^{-1}d^{-1}$ on average in the FTS, MMS, and RAS fish tanks, respectively. The average numbers of bacteria supplied to the larval tanks with the incoming water were $8 \times 10^8 \pm 3 \times 10^8$, $4 \times 10^8 \pm 2 \times 10^8$, and $119 \times 10^8 \pm 63 \times 10^8$ cells $L^{-1}d^{-1}$, respectively, in the FTS, MMS, and RAS. The influence of the internal production of the bacteria was higher than that of the bacteria from incoming water for both FTS and MMS (Fig. 5 b). However, in RAS, the influence of internal bacterial production was less important and was only pronounced during the early rotifer phase, when the tank dilution rates were low.

3.1.6. Qualitative influence of the bacterial communities of the incoming water and live feed on the bacterial community composition of the rearing tank water

To examine the qualitative influence of bacterial communities from incoming water and live feed on the bacterial composition within the rearing tank, we used data from Attramadal et al. (2014) and Vestrum et al. (2020). In these publications, the bacterial compositions of the live feed and incoming water were not directly compared with that of the rearing water in the fish tanks, which is the focus of the current paper.

The qualitative impact of bacteria originating from incoming water and live feed on the bacterial community composition of the water in rearing tanks is shown in Fig. 6. The bacterial community composition of the rearing water in the FTS and MMS had a lower similarity to the bacterial community composition in both the incoming water and the live feed (Bray-Curtis similarity <0.5) than the RAS. This is expected, as most of the incoming water in the RAS is reused, although treated water from the tanks. In the FTS, the analysis found no statistically significant differences in the similarity between the feed and incoming water microbiota compared to the rearing water microbiota ($p = 0.39$). In the MMS, the feed microbiota showed more similarity to the rearing water microbiota than to the incoming water microbiota ($p = 0.05$). In

contrast, the analysis identified significant differences in the RAS, where the incoming water microbiota was more similar to the rearing water microbiota than the feed microbiota ($p = 4.1 \times 10^{-5}$).

3.2. Quantitative assessment of larval uptake of bacteria with live feed versus drinking water

To quantify larval uptake of bacteria with live feed, we used a spreadsheet model to estimate the consumption of live feed per larvae (Supplementary_file_1: sheet_1.1, sheet_1.2, sheet_1.5, and sheet_1.6; materials and methods: 2.1.3 and 2.2). The average number of planktonic bacteria uptaken per larva per day with drinking was estimated to be 6×10^4 in FTS, 6×10^4 in MMS, and 40×10^4 in RAS (Supplementary_file_1, sheet_1.1 and sheet_1.2). In comparison, the average number of bacteria ingested with the live feed per larva per day was estimated to be 500×10^4 (Supplementary_file_1, sheet_1.1 and sheet_1.2). Thus, independent of the rearing system, bacteria associated with the live feed dominated the uptake of bacteria by the larvae (Fig. 7). Bacteria taken up by drinking never exceeded 5 % of the total bacteria uptake. The largest relative impact from the consumption of rearing water bacteria by drinking compared to live feed bacteria was in the early rearing period. Compared to the FTS and MMS, there was a relatively higher uptake of bacteria from the water in RAS, averaging 3.28 %, nearly four times higher than that in FTS and MMS. The average bacterial uptake from the water in FTS and MMS were 0.86 % and 0.75 %, respectively.

3.3. Biofilter-biofilm communities' effects on the bacterial densities and composition of the water leaving the biofilter

3.3.1. Effect of biofilter dilution rate and biofilm on planktonic bacterial densities and composition in the water leaving the biofilter

We conducted Experiment 2.1 using four bioreactors—two with biofilm carriers (at 12 °C and 20 °C) and two without biofilm carriers (at 12 °C and 20 °C)—to examine the effect of biofilter dilution rate and

Fig. 5. Estimated flows of bacteria to larval tanks and internal production of bacteria in tanks for the three rearing systems: FTS, MMS, and RAS. **5a:** Estimated bacterial inflow (number L⁻¹d⁻¹) for the first 30 days post-hatching (dph) **5b:** Estimated flows of bacteria to larval tanks (in) and production of bacteria in the tanks (prod) at selected time points during the first feeding period (with increasing dph and dilution rates (D, tank volume exchanged per day, d⁻¹). Rotifer feeding phase was from 3 to 21 dph, and *Artemia* feeding phase was 22–30 dph. Some data presented in this figure were sourced from [Attramadal et al. \(2014\)](#), while most of the data were not detailed in that paper.

biofilm on planktonic bacterial densities and composition in the water in/leaving the biofilter. Flow cytometry analyses showed that the bio-reactors with matured biofilm carriers delivered about the same number of bacteria per mL in the outgoing water when the dilution rate increased from 1 to 0.1 d⁻¹ at both 12 °C ($p = 0.0987$) and 20 °C ($p = 0.522$), indicating that the dilution rate is not of key importance to the bacterial concentration of the water leaving the biofilter (Fig. 8). The presence of matured biofilm carriers significantly reduced the number of planktonic bacteria in the water volume in the bioreactors by 83 % and 64 % at 12 and 20 °C, respectively, compared to reactors without carriers (Figs. 8 and 9).

The PCoA and boxplot were presented based on the Bray-Curtis similarity of the OTU/sample matrix data (Fig. 10). A two-way PERMANOVA test revealed that the bacterial composition of the water in reactors containing biofilm carriers differed significantly from the bacterial composition in the biofilm on carriers ($p = 0.0052$), with 18 % of the variance in the data explained by this factor. Similar results were obtained using Sørensen similarity ($p = 0.0005$, 15 % of the variance). The temperature did not significantly influence the microbial composition of the biofilm carriers or the water in reactors containing biofilm carriers (Bray-Curtis and Sørensen; $p = 0.1234$ and 0.0662). The biofilm communities on carriers had significantly different relative abundance and OTU inventory compared to the microbiota in the reactor water. The bacterial composition of the water in reactors with or without biofilm carriers differed significantly at both 12 ($p = 0.0305$) and 20 °C ($p = 0.02857$), explaining 54 % and 35 % of the variance in the data, respectively. Similar results were obtained when using Sørensen similarity. This indicates that biofilm carriers significantly impacted the

water microbiota in the reactors, independent of temperature. In conclusion, the presence of the biofilm on carriers significantly influenced the relative abundance and OTU inventory of the water of the reactor.

Some bacterial classes, such as Bacilli and Acidobacteria_Gp10, were relatively more abundant both in the biofilm on carriers (relative abundance: 30 % and 1.2 %) and in the water of reactors with biofilm carriers (relative abundance: 7.2 % and 2.8 %) compared to reactors without biofilm carriers (relative abundance: 1.7 % and 0.02 %) at 12 °C. A similar trend was observed at 20 °C (Supplementary_file_2: supplementary fig. 6a). Furthermore, both the biofilm and the water in reactors with carriers showed a higher abundance of OTU 14 (*Bacillus*), OTU 33 (*Bacillus*), and OTU 8 (unclassified family: Hyphomicrobiaceae) (relative abundance: 16.4 %, 12.7 %, and 15.4 % in biofilm, and 4.2 %, 1.8 %, and 18.6 % in water) compared to the water in reactors without biofilm carriers (relative abundance: 0.01 %, 0.002 %, and 0.2 %) at 12 °C. A similar trend was observed at 20 °C (Supplementary_file_2: supplementary fig. 6b). Finally, the exponential Shannon index, an indicator of microbial richness and evenness, was significantly higher in the water from reactors containing biofilm carriers compared to those without carriers at both temperatures ($p = 0.02$ at 12 °C and $p = 0.03$ at 20 °C) (Supplementary_file_2: supplementary fig. 7).

Biofilm and water shared a higher number of OTUs (Supplementary_file_2: supplementary fig. 8). At 12 °C, the biofilm of the carriers shared 29.6 % of its OTUs only with the water in reactors with carriers but just 2.3 % only with the water in reactors without carriers. At 20 °C, this was even more pronounced, as the biofilm of carriers shared 48.4 % of its OTUs only with the water from reactors with

Fig. 6. Boxplot showing the Bray-Curtis similarities of the microbial community composition of the water in rearing tanks compared with the incoming live feed and water, respectively, in three experimental rearing systems for Atlantic cod larvae: FTS, MMS, and RAS. Comparison of feed microbiota and incoming water microbiota with rearing water microbiota was conducted using the Wilcoxon rank-sum test. The data utilized in this study were sourced from [Attramadal et al. \(2014\)](#) and [Vestrum et al. \(2020\)](#). Importantly, the referenced publications did not directly compare the bacterial compositions of the live feed and incoming water with those of the rearing water in fish tanks, which is our focus in this study.

carriers and just 1.2 % only with the water from reactors without carriers. Out of the total unique OTU reads within each sample type, one unique OTU dominated in water in reactors without biofilm carriers, OTU_164 (*Staphylococcus*) at 12 °C and OTU_347 (*Alteromonas*) at 20 °C with 41.3 and 81 %, respectively (**Supplementary file 2: supplementary fig. 9**). This indicated that the absence of biofilm favours r-strategists in the water, leading to the dominance of a single species due to the availability of sufficient dissolved organic matter (DOM) in the reactor and that this effect increases with temperature due to an increase in maximum specific growth rate.

Furthermore, we examined the effect of the effective surface area of biofilm carriers on the density of planktonic bacteria in the water (Experiment 2.4). Flow cytometry analyses showed that the reactors with the highest effective surface area had a 46 % reduction in planktonic bacteria compared to reactors with almost half the effective surface area of biofilm carriers ($8 \pm 6 \times 10^6$ versus $4 \pm 3 \times 10^6$ bacteria mL^{-1}) (**Fig. 11**). This supports the hypothesis that matured biofilms decrease the concentration of planktonic bacteria through their competitive consumption of organic matter.

3.3.2. Release dynamics of bacterial cells from matured biofilm carriers and variations in bacterial community composition between biofilm, water, and released particles

We quantified released bacteria from matured biofilm carriers and analyzed community composition in biofilm, water, and released particles (Experiment 2.3) using four bioreactors with carriers matured under varying organic loads and temperatures. The release of bacterial cells from carriers ($\text{cells cm}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$) was found to be 47 % higher from carriers previously exposed to high organic loading compared to those with low organic loading (**Fig. 12**). Biofilm carriers incubated at 20 °C exhibited a marginal increase (1.4 %) in bacterial cell released compared to those incubated at 12 °C. The average release rate was 1.3

$\times 10^2$ cells $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$ from carriers when the initial biofilm density was estimated to be 2.4×10^4 cells cm^{-2} . This release rate corresponded to approximately 0.6 % of the total biofilm cells per hour.

Both single planktonic bacteria and biofilm aggregates were released from the biofilm carriers during the test period. The bacterial community composition differed between the biofilm on carriers, the planktonic bacteria in the water ($<3.0 \mu\text{m}$ particles), and the bacteria in the biofilm particles in water ($>3.0 \mu\text{m}$). However, the change in the bacteria profiles between the high and low nutrient loading was in the same direction for all three habitats (biofilm, particles, and water) in the NMDS plot (**Fig. 13**).

4. Discussion

This study focused on a quantitative and qualitative evaluation of the importance of various bacterial sources on the density and composition of the bacterial community of the rearing water and the digestive tract of fish larvae. Sources of bacteria considered included incoming water, biofilm, microalgae, live feed, and bacterial growth occurring within rearing water, and we considered three different system designs: FTS, MMS, and RAS. Knowledge regarding the quantitative and qualitative assessment of the various bacterial sources should form the basis for microbial management, yet it is currently lacking. Therefore, our aim was to provide a solid and updated basis for academic discussion, as well as technological and operational improvements for microbial management within the aquaculture industry.

Different rearing system designs resulted in varying concentrations and compositions of bacteria in both the rearing water and the water flowing into the rearing tank. A key finding was that the addition of microalgae was a major source of bacteria for the rearing tank water, particularly in FTS and MMS. Thus, when used, microalgae can be the most significant contributor of bacteria to the rearing water, particularly

Fig. 7. Proportion of the ingested bacteria per larva per day coming from drinking water and feeding on the live feed, respectively, at different days post-hatch (dph) with different tank dilution rates (D, tank volumes exchanged, d^{-1}). The data to determine the bacterial ingestion with live feed by fish larvae was based on the spreadsheet model (Supplementary_file_1, sheet_1.5, sheet_1.6), and literature for drinking rate (Mangor-Jensen and Adoff, 1987; Tytler and Blaxter, 1988), uptake of bacteria related to drinking rate number of bacteria per mL (Supplementary_file_1, sheet_1.1, sheet_1.2 and sheet_1.4) or individual rotifer (Skjermo and Vadstein, 1993) and *Artemia* (Olsen et al., 2000), and bacteria density in rearing water (Attramadal et al., 2014).

in the early feeding period when the water exchange rate is low. Another influential factor at low tank water exchange rates (HRT of 1 h or more) was the internal growth of bacteria within the rearing tanks. This process is often overlooked, and we are unaware of other studies investigating bacterial production in rearing tanks. Other studies have shown that when dilution rates were high (around 15 to 20 min), the role of internal bacterial growth in rearing tanks diminished. In contrast, the importance of growth and detachment of sessile bacteria adhering to system surfaces increased (Dahle et al., 2022).

It is essential to manage the availability of organic matter to control bacterial growth in rearing systems, as it serves as the primary growth-limiting substrate for heterotrophic bacteria. DOM supplied by feed, algae, faecal matter, and decomposing remnants of egg and larval remains influenced the bacterial abundance in rearing tanks (Attramadal et al., 2012c; Vadstein et al., 1993). Controlling the internal growth of bacteria can be done by reducing the supply of the organic substrates to the water volume, thereby decreasing the microbial carrying capacity of the system (Fossmark et al., 2020; Vadstein et al., 1993). It was shown that adding organic matter in the form of algal paste or live algae increased the abundance of bacteria in larval tanks more than adding inorganic clay (Attramadal et al., 2012c). Internal bacterial growth is also triggered by the pulse of organic substrates released when eggs hatch in the larval tanks. A 1000-fold increase in bacteria (CFU/mL) has been shown during the hatching of eggs (Hansen and Olafsen, 1989). The supply of organic substrates increases with stocking density. A sudden increase in the supply of organic matter may stimulate the growth of detrimental opportunistic bacteria. Consequently, egg hatching in the first feeding tanks should be avoided, especially if the stocking density is high.

We found that the supply of bacteria with incoming water to fish tanks was a major source of bacteria for the rearing water in RAS. In the initial production phase, this contribution was estimated to be comparable to that of the internal production of bacteria, and as the dilution rate of the tank increased with larval growth, it took over as the most important source of bacteria. This suggests that controlling or manipulating the bacterial composition and load of the incoming (and initial fill-up) water can be key to microbial control in the rearing tanks. In addition, the early phase is a significant occasion to influence the bacterial colonization of the newly hatched, uncolonized larvae. In support of our findings, it was shown that if the water in the RAS was disinfected right before entering the rearing tanks and the dilution rate was low, the microbial composition of the rearing water became more similar to that of the FTS and MMS. This was due to a low influx of water and the dominant regrowth by opportunistic bacteria in the rearing tank (Attramadal et al., 2021).

For the initial cultivation phase with stagnant to low dilution of the tank water, the significant load of bacteria introduced with rotifers and microalgae can offer an opportunity to influence the microbial community in the rearing tank in contact with and entering the larvae. This control could be achieved by carefully preparing and manipulating bacteria in and on the live feed (Makridis et al., 2000) and microalgae while selecting an effective water treatment method for the initial stage. In practice, this could be done by filling tanks with matured RAS water or by feeding and maturing the water in the rearing tanks for some days prior to the transfer of eggs or preferably larvae. The live feed route of bacteria to the rearing water and guts of the larvae can be optimized by the culture conditions of the live feed. This could include grazing on live algae cultures (Olsen et al., 2000) and/or treatment with probiotics

Fig. 8. The density of planktonic bacteria was determined by flow cytometry analyses in the outflowing water from seawater reactors operated with (present) and without (absent) matured biofilm carriers at 12 and 20 °C in an experiment (Experiment 2.1) where the dilution was increased stepwise. The flow rate was initially set at 12.5 mL/h, equal to a dilution rate of one reactor volume per day (HRT of 24 h). The dilution rate was increased stepwise: from an initial dilution of 1 d⁻¹ (HRT of 24 h for 15 days) to one volume exchanged every 0.47 d⁻¹ (11.3 h HRT for 21 days), one volume exchanged every 0.21 d⁻¹ (5 h HRT for 14 days), and finally one volume exchanged every 0.1 d⁻¹ (HRT of 2.4 h for 6 days). Error bars indicate standard deviations. One-way ANOVA showed that the dilution rate had no significant impact on planktonic bacterial densities in the presence of matured and active biofilm carriers at both 12 °C ($p = 0.0987$) and 20 °C ($p = 0.522$).

(Skjermo et al., 2015), as well as washing and disinfection procedures (Munro et al., 1993).

The similarity between the microbiota of the rearing water and that of the live feed in RAS was found to be low in this study (analysis of previously unpublished results from Attramadal et al., 2014). In RAS,

the water coming into the rearing tanks is mostly the rearing water that has been treated and biofiltered. In this study, we found that bacterial regrowth relative to the bacteria from incoming water to rearing tanks is reduced in RAS compared to FTS and MMS. Thus, the RAS design counteracts regrowth in the rearing tank and leads to high similarity in microbial community composition between the incoming and rearing tank water. In addition, water retention time in the whole RAS is, per definition, high due to the recirculation of treated rearing water and low levels of water exchange, which allows and favours slow-growing K-strategic planktonic bacteria to remain and compete for the organic matter in the system (Attramadal et al., 2014). In this study, we did not consider the case of disinfection of the reused water flow that may be one of the components of the water treatment loop in RAS, which may change the dynamics completely and has been shown to counteract the described effects (Attramadal et al., 2012a).

Although the MMS includes a biofilter, it lacks the return route of planktonic bacteria to the rearing tanks and the extensive HRT characterizing RAS. Maybe even more importantly, the MMS has a larger difference in the microbial carrying capacity between the incoming water to the tank and the rearing water than RAS unless the biofilter is intentionally fed to increase the microbial carrying capacity (Attramadal et al., 2016). This feature of RAS has important implications for the environment of the fish, as it reduces the opening for uncontrolled regrowth of harmful fast-growing bacteria in the rearing water (Attramadal et al., 2014; Vadstein et al., 2018b).

The uptake of bacteria by the larvae involves both an active uptake from the water (Reitan et al., 1998) and uptake through ingestion of live feed. The uptake of bacteria from the water was less than from the live feed in all the investigated systems. However, the uptake of bacteria from the rearing water was relatively higher in RAS compared to FTS and MMS, and the difference was most pronounced at young larval stages. Even though the quantitative uptake of bacteria from the live feed was higher than from the water, larval microbiota was found to be more similar to the microbiota of the rearing water than that of the live feed microbiota (Bakke et al., 2013; Vestrum et al., 2018). On the other hand, different live feed diets (rotifers or copepods) did not lead to significant differences in the composition of the microbiota of Atlantic

Fig. 9. Density of planktonic bacteria in the outflowing water from reactors with and without matured biofilm carriers at 12 and 20 °C in an experiment (Experiment 2.1) run for 56 days with seawater as determined by flow cytometry. Water samples were collected from each of the four reactors (two reactors with biofilm carriers at 12 and 20 °C, and two reactors without biofilm carriers at 12 and 20 °C) at intervals of 2–3 days until 56 days. The Wilcoxon rank sum ($p = 1.5 \times 10^{-13}$ at 12 °C; $p = 6.8 \times 10^{-9}$ at 20 °C) and Kruskal-Wallis tests ($p = 1.4 \times 10^{-13}$ at 12 °C; $p = 6.6 \times 10^{-9}$ at 20 °C) showed that the production of planktonic bacteria was significantly higher in the reactor without biofilm carriers at both temperatures. The temperature significantly affected the bacterial cell density both when biofilm carriers were present (Wilcoxon rank sum ($p = 0.04$) and Kruskal-Wallis test ($p = 0.04$)) and absent (Wilcoxon rank sum ($p = 1.8 \times 10^{-7}$) and Kruskal-Wallis test ($p = 1.7 \times 10^{-7}$)).

(a) PCoA based on Bray–Curtis similarity

(b) Boxplot showing pairwise Bray–Curtis similarity

Fig. 10. PCoA (a) and boxplot (b) based on Bray-Curtis similarity of bacterial community composition in the biofilm on carriers and in the seawater in reactors with or without biofilm carriers at 12 and 20 °C during Experiment 2.1. The presentation included four water samples from reactors with biofilm carriers for each temperature condition (12 and 20 °C) and four biofilm carrier samples for each reactor at the same temperature conditions. Additionally, four water samples from reactors without biofilm carriers operated at 12 °C, and three samples at 20 °C, were included.

cod larvae (Bakke et al., 2019; Bakke et al., 2013). This contrasts with prior research that has highlighted the significance of diet in influencing the gut microbiota of fish (Mouchet et al., 2012; Sullam et al., 2012), but without comparing the effects of the live feed to the effect of the water microbiota. It could be that feed and water microbiota affect the microbiota of fish differently at different developmental stages. Bakke et al. (2017) showed that the microbiota in developing Atlantic cod larvae exhibited substantial temporal variations that could not be

accounted for by alterations in the environmental microbiota. They suggested that developmental modifications in the intestine and the immune system play an imperative role in shaping the composition of the larval microbiota. Another study conducted on juvenile Nile tilapia demonstrated that diet types (live feed vs plant-based feed) had a substantial effect on the gut microbiota during the early life stages (Wang et al., 2022). They suggested that modulation of the gut microbiota could be possible in the earlier stages through dietary interventions. This

Fig. 11. Boxplot showing the density of planktonic bacteria as determined by flow cytometry in the water of 300 mL reactors with either an effective surface area of carriers of 343 cm² (Low surface area treatment) or an effective surface area of carriers of 666 cm² (High surface area treatment) fed nutrient stock for 12 weeks (Experiment 2.4). The Wilcoxon rank sum ($p = 0.0045$) and Kruskal-Wallis test ($p = 0.0055$) showed that the density of planktonic bacteria was significantly higher in the water of the reactors with a relatively lower biofilm surface area of carriers. Each treatment included three replicate reactors.

Fig. 12. Development in bacterial release (cell cm⁻² h⁻¹) from biofilm carriers in separate reactors after incubation at different temperatures and with different levels of nutrient supply (Experiment 2.3): a) Biofilm carriers exposed to 12 °C and b) 20 °C with similar nutrient conditions of M65 medium (33.3 μL of M65 medium from medium stock solution of 150 g/L) with a flowrate of 12.5 mL/h for 56 days. c) Biofilm carriers incubated at room temperature and receiving high nutrient treatment (165 μL of M65 medium to reactor three times a week for 84 days), d) Biofilm carriers incubated at room temperature and receiving low nutrient treatment (55 μL of M65 medium to reactor three times a week for 106 days). M65 medium stock solution used was 150 g/L.

implies that during the earlier life stages of juvenile fish, the gut microbiota is influenced by environmental microbiota from live feed and rearing water, the type of feed, as well as by host selection and microbe/microbe interactions in the gut.

Rotifers and *Artemia* are filter feeders that, to some extent, ingest bacteria (Makridis et al., 2000; Vadstein et al., 2018a). The sustained exchange of bacteria between the tank water and the live feed may, therefore, blur the distinction between the bacteria originating from the

live feed and those from the rearing tank. However, some of the live feed is likely ingested relatively fast before their gut bacteria are exchanged completely with that of the rearing water (Olsen et al., 2000). This study did not consider the exchange of bacteria between the live feed and the rearing water. Therefore, what we showed in our results is the estimated maximum influence from the bacteria initially associated with the live feed and, hence, the minimum influence from the rearing water bacteria entering the larval digestive tract. Furthermore, our study did not

Fig. 13. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) of the Bray-Curtis similarity between bacterial communities in water (<math><3.0\ \mu\text{m}</math> particles, open squares), biofilm particles in water (>3.0 μm particles, open circles), and biofilm on carriers (crosses) collected at the end of Experiment 2.3 from reactors containing biofilm carriers originating from Experiment 2.2. In Experiment 2.3, biofilm carriers from Experiment 2.2 were collected to quantify bacterial release from carriers treated under two different organic loading levels at room temperature. For the low-nutrient treatment, 55 μL of seawater M65 medium was added to a reactor three times a week for 106 days, after which the carriers were collected for the first release experiment (Experiment 2.3). After the first release experiment (Experiment 2.3), the biofilm carriers used in the experiment were returned to the same reactor, which had been treated with low nutrients in Experiment 2.2. All carriers in the same bioreactor were then exposed to a high-nutrient treatment (165 μL of M65 medium, three times a week) for the next 84 days. At the end of this period, biofilm carriers representing the high-nutrient treatment were collected for the second release experiment (Experiment 2.3). The original concentration of the seawater M65 medium stock used was 150 g/L.

consider the influence of bacteria released from the faeces of the live feed and fish larvae on the water microbial community. However, the relative distinction between the live feed microbiota, water microbiota, and larval microbiota over time observed in this study and [Attramadal et al. \(2014\)](#) suggests that the impact of the defecated bacteria from larvae and the live feed is of minor importance. Future research may help to nuance this conclusion.

The unique features of RAS, including the presence of both biofilters and water reuse, contributed to a greater similarity between the microbiota of the rearing water and the water entering the tanks, as compared to FTS and MMS ([Attramadal et al., 2014](#)). Several studies have shown a negative correlation between the quantity of suspended bacteria in the water of RAS and the number of bacteria and thickness of biofilm growing on the biofilter media ([Leonard et al., 2000](#); [Michaud et al., 2006](#)). Our results supported previous studies showing that matured bacterial communities in biofilms can consume new supplies of organic carbon quickly and efficiently and compete effectively for the available carbon with bacteria suspended in the water ([Pedersen et al., 2010](#); [Rojas-Tirado et al., 2019](#)). [Rojas-Tirado et al. \(2019\)](#) observed that RAS without biofilters showed significant increases in the number of bacteria after the addition of a spike of DOM compared to RAS with matured biofilters. The most likely explanation for this is that a substantial biomass of attached bacteria in the biofilter had a large capacity to consume organic matter. This, in turn, reduced the availability of DOM, fostering high competition and lowering the microbial carrying capacity of the water, which hindered a large increase in planktonic bacteria numbers. This phenomenon was referred to as a “buffer effect” by the authors, referring to the biofilm handling sudden peaks in the organic matter supply without leading to spikes in bacteria density in

the system water ([Rojas-Tirado et al., 2019](#)). In this way, the biofilter indirectly contributes to favouring slower-growing, highly competitive K-strategists over r-strategists in the rearing water, which will ultimately improve fish performance ([Vadstein et al., 2018b](#)).

Our bioreactor experiment (Experiment 2.1) demonstrated that the dilution rate did not significantly affect the density of planktonic bacteria in the outlet water from reactors containing matured biofilm carriers. The biofilm in matured biofilter carriers effectively consumed the given DOM dose and produced a relatively consistent bacterial output. This occurred even at a high water dilution rate, as the dilution rate does not affect the loss rate of bacteria—but only the supply rate of DOM.

We demonstrated that biofilm on carriers played a crucial role in structuring water microbiota, both directly through bacterial release and indirectly through chemical conversions (Experiment 2.1). Temperatures (12 and 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) significantly influenced the density and the composition of the water microbiota of the reactors, as could be expected ([Sergaliev et al., 2021](#)). We found that the bacterial composition of the water in reactors with biofilm carriers significantly differed from that in reactors without carriers at both 12 and 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. This indicates that biofilm carriers significantly impacted the water microbiota in reactors with biofilm carriers at both temperatures. Biofilter-biofilm communities influence the water microbiota indirectly through chemical conversions, such as nitrification and organic matter consumption, which alter the selection regime in the water ([Bakke et al., 2017](#); [Schreier et al., 2010](#); [Vadstein et al., 2018a, 2018b](#)). Also, biofilm carriers can directly affect water microbiota by releasing bacteria from the biofilm into the water, further contributing to the observed differences.

We found that the bacterial composition in the water of reactors with biofilm carriers differed significantly from that in reactors without

carriers (Experiment 2.1). Unique microenvironments within the biofilm may create different selection forces compared to the water habitat, leading to different selection pressures for the microbiota (McDougald et al., 2012). Notably, nutrient concentrations and oxygen availability can vary in these microenvironments (McDougald et al., 2012; Suarez et al., 2019). Previous studies have also reported that the microbiota of the rearing water and biofilm carriers differs in RAS (Bakke et al., 2017; Dahle et al., 2023).

Our results showed that temperature (12 °C versus 20 °C) did not significantly influence the microbial composition of either the biofilm on carriers or the water in contact with biofilm carriers (Experiment 2.1). This indicates that the biofilm carriers provided a stable environment for the microbial communities, shielding them against temperature variations from 12 to 20 °C. The influence of biofilm communities likely stabilizes the water microbiota, potentially surpassing the effect of temperature. Other factors, such as nutrient availability or biofilm maturity, may play a more critical role in shaping these communities than the temperature in our experimental set-up.

Our findings also demonstrated that some bacterial classes, such as Acidobacteria_Gp10 and Bacilli, had relatively higher abundance in both the biofilm and the associated water of reactors at 12 and 20 °C compared to the water in reactors without biofilm carriers (Experiment 2.1). OTU 14 (*Bacillus*), OTU 33 (*Bacillus*), and OTU 8 (an unclassified family within Hyphomicrobiaceae) were more abundant in both the biofilm and in the water in reactors with than without biofilm carriers at both temperatures. This suggested a potential association of these bacteria with the biofilm environment, where they might be either released from the biofilm matrix or selectively enriched in the biofilm-associated water. The higher microbial richness and evenness observed in water in reactors containing biofilm carriers indicate that biofilm significantly enhanced community diversity, likely through the same mechanisms of bacterial release and/or selection. Previous studies have reported that biofilm enhanced the diversity of the water microbiota in RAS (Attramadal et al., 2014; Attramadal et al., 2012a; Attramadal et al., 2012b). In this study, single unique opportunistic OTUs dominated the water in reactors without biofilm carriers, and this effect increases with temperature due to an increase in maximum specific growth rate. This indicates that the absence of biofilm resulted in low competition for resources and thus r-selection, favouring fast-growing, opportunistic heterotrophs (r-strategists) in the water. Exposure of larvae to a high fraction of r-strategists increased detrimental interactions with the fish (Vadstein et al., 2018b; Vadstein et al., 1993).

From Experiment 2.3, we found that temperature and organic loading affected the quantitative flow of bacteria released from biofilm carriers to the water. Higher temperatures and a higher load of readily available nutrients may facilitate the growth of a thicker biofilm and result in higher release rates of bacteria. The higher release rate observed from the biofilm after transfer to the particle-free water could also be attributed to the sudden reduction in nutrients experienced by the bacterial community of the biofilm (Hunt et al., 2004; Nagar and Schwarz, 2015). Biofilms offer protection for the bacteria, but when conditions become unfavourable, bacteria can disperse and become suspended to find new colonization sites (McDougald et al., 2012). This dispersal is regulated by signalling molecules in response to environmental changes. Gene expression is altered, producing enzymes and surfactants that break down the biofilm matrix, allowing bacteria to grow planktonically (McDougald et al., 2012). This planktonic bacterial growth benefits from higher metabolism and increased mobility (Lewis, 2010; Nagar and Schwarz, 2015). We found that the microbiota associated with the biofilm on carriers, water, and aggregates differed from each other. Despite these differences, the analysis of the microbial communities also revealed that the microbiota of these different categories responded in a similar way to nutrient additions at high and low levels, indicating that nutrient availability may affect bacterial communities consistently across different habitats in the system.

Bacterial interactions in biofilms, including quorum sensing, are

poorly understood and need further studies. The organic matter/microbial carrying capacity “buffering” and modification potential of biofilters on the water microbiota need to be considered when developing strategies to control microbial water quality in RAS and MMS in the future. Assessing biofilm growth dynamics in biofilters could lead to a better understanding and intentional use of the moderating effect of organic matter/microbial carrying capacity.

5. Conclusions

This study provided insights and a systematic overview of microbial interactions in larviculture that can be valuable for future research and management strategies in land-based aquaculture. Our study demonstrated that considerate preparation and manipulation of the initial bacterial community could affect rearing conditions and provide newly hatched larvae with favourable conditions for bacterial colonization. The initial live feed and the water used to fill the tanks are crucial in structuring the microbial environment during the first day post-hatching, when larvae undergo colonization. These factors can be manipulated to benefit larvae.

We found that for the first weeks in the hatchery, the internal growth of bacteria in the water within rearing tanks substantially impacted the rearing water more than bacteria from incoming water, particularly in FTS and MMS systems, thereby limiting options for external microbial manipulations. In contrast, RAS was the only system where external bacterial sources quantitatively influenced the rearing water microbiota to a comparable extent as the internal growth of bacteria in the fish tank.

For all system designs studied, live feed was the dominant source of bacteria entering the larvae. However, a previous study on Atlantic cod larvae demonstrated that the gut microbiota showed higher similarity to the microbiota of the rearing water than that of the feed. This can be explained by the selection pressure by/in the host. Methods to control the microbiota of both rearing water and live feed are recommended to influence the bacteria present within the larvae.

Our study further showed that the inclusion of biofilters reduced the microbial carrying capacity and the number of bacteria in the water while increasing the richness and evenness of the microbiota. Our findings also indicated that the dilution rate had no significant impact on the density of planktonic bacteria in the outlet water of reactors containing matured biofilm carriers. Moreover, biofilm releases bacteria into the water, moderates organic matter fluctuations within the system, and significantly influences the microbiota of the water both qualitatively and quantitatively. The supply of organic matter affected the bacterial community composition in all habitats, such as water and biofilm carriers and positively correlated with the number of bacteria released from biofilms to the water. In future strategies to control microbial water quality in RAS and MMS, the impact of the biofilter biofilm should be considered.

5.1. Future recommendations

The symbiotic interaction between marine fish larvae and microbes is crucial for producing high-quality juvenile fish in aquaculture. However, intensive rearing situations can create unintended detrimental microbial conditions. Understanding the microbial conditions and interactions is essential for effective microbial management. Our future recommendations can be summarized as follows:

Optimize microbial conditions:

Manipulate the initial bacterial community through considerate preparation and controlled interventions to create the desired microbial conditions in all systems from the start. This could be achieved by filling the rearing tanks with matured RAS water and optimizing the microbiota of live feed before transferring the eggs or preferably larvae to the rearing tanks. Future studies in aquaculture

systems should recognize and account for the substantial impact of internal bacterial growth within the tanks.

Manage water and particles and focus on biofilm stability:

Strategies that optimize microbial carrying capacity should be explored to stabilize and reduce the microbial loads in the water. This can be achieved through improvements in system design and rearing regimes that balance bacterial abundance, maintaining a stable and low organic load in the rearing systems. Effective organic matter management enhances the stability of the biofilm and system microbiota.

Understand the influence of the incoming water on rearing water in tanks:

Further research is essential to comprehensively understand how the bacteria coming in with the incoming water to the tank affects both the rearing water community and the larvae. This knowledge can be utilized to advance more effective management practices.

Explore host-related factors and larval microbiota:

A deeper understanding of the selection pressure from host-related factors influencing larval microbiota can pave the way for more targeted approaches to manipulate and optimize host-microbe interactions.

Explore biofilter functionality further:

Given the numerous critical functions of biofilms and biofilters in rearing systems, research should aim to understand more of the impact of biofilter-biofilm microbiota on microbial water quality, with special focus on the impact on composition and density of microbiota in the rearing water through dispersal from the biofilm. The consumption of DOM by biofilter communities should be operated in a way that secures competition and, thereby, K-selection and release of K-selected species to the water microbiota. This is important when developing future strategies for controlling microbial water quality in RAS and MMS.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sujan Khadka: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Olav Vadstein:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Ingrid Bakke:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Yngvar Olsen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Kari J.K. Attramadal:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors state that there are no financial conflicts or personal relationships that might have affected the research presented in this article.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2025.742445>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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